

Special Relativity and Origins of Quantum Wavelength?

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L. DeBroglie stressed a strong connection with special relativity when predicting that a quantum particle (electron) should exhibit wave behaviour. Wave behaviour is already found in the photon which is a quantum particle arising from Maxwell's equations which are Lorentz invariant. In fact, there are statements in the literature that $dE/dt = \text{grad} \times B$ and $dB/dt = -\text{grad} \times E$ (sourceless Maxwell's equations) are in fact quantum equations for a photon wavefunction of $E+iB$. Furthermore, in $\exp[ipx-iEt]$, $px-Et$ is a Lorentz invariant, although for a bound state $\exp(-iEt)$ remains, but $\exp(ipx)$ is replaced with a momentum distribution $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In a previous note (1), we argued that one may take the relativistic Lagrangian $L = -m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ and write $v=X/T$. With $\exp(i \text{Action}) = \exp(i \int dt L)$ and taking d/dt yields E time $\exp(i \text{Action})$ and $-i d/dx \exp(i \text{Action})$, $p = xp(i \text{Action})$. The relationship $EE=pp + m_0 m_0$ may then be converted into a differential equation, namely the Klein-Gordon equation.

For a free particle, a solution is $\exp(ipx-iEt)$. $\exp(ipx)$ immediately suggests a physical wavelength proportional to $1/p$. The question is how does this wavelength originate? For a photon which has spin 1, one may create circularly polarized light with E and B moving in a plane perpendicular to photon motion with frequency px if t is held fixed. This motion of E and B is said to account for spin and may show a physical reason for a photon wavelength i.e. one related to E and B fields. The Klein-Gordon equation, however, holds for spin 0 particles. We argue in this note that the physical reason for a quantum wavelength may be related to the factor $\sqrt{1-vv/cc}$ from special relativity.

Statistical Scenario

In previous notes, we have argued that quantum mechanics is a statistical theory. It seems to be related to energy and energy flow (momentum) with t and x being considered independent variable. For example, $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ is the wavelength for a free particle. One may consider x and t as independent with a frequency in time related to E and a wavelength (frequency in space) related to p . A free particle should have equal probability to be at any x statistically i.e. $P(x)=\text{constant}$. A similar result holds for $P(t)$. One may argue, however, that more is "going on". For example, $\exp(ipx)$ has a modulus of 1 implying $P(x)=\text{constant}$, but contains dynamics i.e. an oscillatory behaviour with spatial frequency related to p . This result follows from $-i d/dx \exp(ipx) = p \exp(ipx)$ i.e. one argues that a conditional probability changes with x in proportion to the flow of energy (i.e. momentum). This holds both relativistically and non-relativistically, but does not explain the origin of the wavelength proportional to $1/p$.

Lagrangian and Klein-Gordon Equation

The relativistic Lagrangian for a free particle is $-m_0 \sqrt{1-vv}$ ($c=1$) and the action is $-m_0(1-vv)$
T. Writing $v=X/T$ and varying with respect to X and T independently yields:

$$-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action}) \text{ and } i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action}) \quad ((1))$$

as shown in (1). One may then link ((1)) with the Einstein momentum-energy relationship: $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$ to create the Klein-Gordon equation.

We argue that varying with respect to time T and space X is similar to considering independent fluctuations (or errors, variations etc) in the relativistic Action. A key factor in the Lagrangian is $\sqrt{1-v^2}$ because the variation with respect to X only acts on this term. This X variation gives rise to the momentum result in ((1)). $\exp(ipx - iEt)$ is a solution of the Klein-Gordon equation for a free particle, so wavelength $1/p$ results from a fluctuation of X in the $\sqrt{1-v^2}$ term. This term ultimately originates from $m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$. Thus, we argue that whatever physical mechanism occurs, producing $m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$, the same mechanism creates a physical wavelength related to $1/p$.

A photon has a spin of 1 and circularly polarized light has E and B moving in the xy plane (z motion of photon) with a spatial frequency of p for fixed t . Thus, the circularly moving E field (and B) could be related to photon wavelength. The Klein-Gordon equation, however, holds for spin 0 particles and these already have $\exp(ipx)$ and wavelength proportional to $1/p$. Thus, rotational arguments may not be needed.

By suggesting that the physical origin of a quantum wavelength follows from the mechanism which creates the free particle special relativistic energy $m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$, quantum mechanics and special relativity become closely linked.

Conclusion

In conclusion, in this note we argue that the idea of a quantum wavelength of a free particle proportional to $1/p$ from $\exp(ipx)$ follows from the Klein-Gordon equation. $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ for a free particle is $\exp(i (-m \sqrt{1-v^2})T)$ where $v=X/T$. Varying X and T independently yields $-i \frac{d}{dx} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = p \exp(i \text{ Action})$ and $i \frac{d}{dt} \exp(i \text{ Action}) = E \exp(i \text{ Action})$. These may be combined with $E^2 = p^2 + m^2$. The argument we make is that $p \exp(i \text{ Action})$ follows directly from an X fluctuation (or variation) in the factor $\sqrt{1-v^2}$. This factor is present because of the relativistic free particle energy $m/\sqrt{1-v^2}$. Thus, we argue that whatever mechanism is responsible for creating $\sqrt{1-v^2}$ is also responsible for creating the quantum wavelength.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Klein Gordon Equation, $\exp(i \text{ Action})$ Propagator and Fluctuations (preprint, zenodo, 2021) <https://www.zenodo.org/record/4706004#.YL-2aWjYoWU>